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Quality assurance of Master's theses at a large engineering faculty.

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ABSTRACT

The Faculty of Engineering Science at KU Leuven is responsible for 29 Master's programmes (incl. 5 Advanced Master's), educating over 5000 students. In this context, quality assurance faces many challenges, not only because of its numerous programmes, but also due to varying student characteristics and student numbers per programme. In the paper presented, the quality assurance of the Master's thesis will be highlighted.

A Master's thesis is an essential part of an academically oriented programme, since it integrates knowledge and skills connected to a certain discipline. It is a research project in which students show whether they have acquired the appropriate academic competences to contribute independently to scientific research.

The core of the Master's thesis quality assurance is the "Faculty committee of Master's theses" who formulates its policy regarding organisation and quality assurance of the thesis. Over the last years, efforts have been made, especially in terms of learning outcomes, of a learning pathway regarding reporting skills, evaluation and mentoring students. The latter resulted in an elaborated educational support programme for supervising teaching assistants (TAs).

This paper will give an overview on how the Faculty's policy was formulated and subsequent actions that have been taken regarding quality assurance of the Master's thesis, without compromising every Master's programme own habits and traditions. Specific attention will be given to the educational support programme for supervising TAs. Finally, future plans will be discussed.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Quality assurance, Curriculum development

Keywords: Master's thesis, Quality Assurance, Coaching TAs, Reporting skills

INTRODUCTION

At the Faculty of Engineering Science the Master's thesis is an essential part of the Master programmes. Each Master's student has to complete a Master's thesis of 24 credits during the final master's stage. Since one academic year typically corresponds to 60 credits, a Master's thesis forms a major part of the programme. Since a Master's thesis has a considerable research component, most Master's theses are therefore conducted in the research labs of the Faculty. Besides, a fair number of Master's thesis are performed in collaboration with industry, or a Master's thesis can also be carried out abroad as part of an Erasmus+ exchange. A major concern of the Faculty is to assure the quality of these Master's theses, taking into account varying student characteristics and student numbers as well as each programme own habits and traditions.

1 FACULTY COMMITTEE RESPONSIBLE FOR THE MASTER'S THESIS

The core of the Master's thesis quality assurance is the Faculty committee responsible for the Master's thesis (FCMT) who formulates its policy regarding organisation and quality assurance of the thesis. This committee reports to the Faculty Educational Committee (FEC) that consist of all programme directors and is headed by the vice-dean Education. The committee itself is composed out of representatives of each programme, the TA's and the students. It is chaired by the vice-dean Education, and the secretariat is taken care of by the educational development unit of the Faculty.

The committee started out as a rather administrative and practical consultative but as quality assurance became more prominent on the Faculty's agenda, it's mandate became more policy-focused. Over the last years, efforts have been made, in terms of refining admission procedures, formulating learning outcomes, developing a learning pathway regarding reporting skills, evaluation and mentoring students. The latter resulted in an elaborated educational support programme for supervising teaching assistants.

1.1 Admission procedures

Each Master's programme has its own procedure to assign Master's thesis topics to students. However, to ensure uniformity, some elements are shared by all Master's programmes organised by the Faculty. During the spring semester of the first Master's stage, a list of possible topics for Master's theses is announced to the students through an online platform. In most programmes students can propose their own topic, if they find a professor who is associated with the programme and willing to act as advisor. Students are encouraged to contact researchers and professors to make an informed choice about the thesis topic they would like to pursue. For example, in some programmes this can be done during a theses fair, where coaches and supervisors are present. The topics are assigned to the students before the end of June, taking into

account the preferences of the students and a fair distribution of the theses over the Faculty staff.

1.2 Learning outcomes

At the Faculty, every course is described in an ECTS course description. This file is available on the programme website. It contains a full course description, including the goals and learning outcomes of the course, the content, teaching and evaluation methods. Concerning quality assurance, well defined learning outcomes are crucial. Therefore, the committee refined the learning outcomes of the Master's thesis, in close cooperation with all stakeholders: professors, teaching assistants, students and industrial partners. This exercise resulted in learning outcomes acceptable and recognisable for all programmes:

After completion of the Master's thesis, the student:

- has set up an original research (original in the sense that the student has generated (partly) new knowledge);
- has state-of-the-art knowledge regarding the topic of his research;
- formulates the research question clearly and correctly;
- follows the developments in the field independently and can assess their relevance for answering the research question(s);
- designs a research plan, using the most appropriate and achievable techniques (based on the information found in the scientific literature) and executes it;
- analyses and interprets the obtained results;
- has a critical attitude towards (own) research results;
- considers optimization (context and (suboptimal) prerequisites) and always keeps track of uncertainties to define boundary conditions;
- can report about his research in a coherent way, where adequate attention is given to: correctness of the displayed information (state-of-the-art), understandable and clear within the discipline, scientific language, correct Dutch or English, the layout of the text, references, tables and figures that meet the specified formal requirements, etc.;
- has an academic correct attitude in relation to references;
- creates a decision-making process where the obtained results are framed in relation to the state-of-the-art (also demonstrating what the student has imparted to the state-of-the-art);
- can report orally about his research, in which due consideration is given to: situating the research within the discipline, presenting in an attractive way, the structure and coherence of the presentation, the scientific language, respecting the time constraints;
- can answer in scientifically correct language to questions from both fellow students and researchers from the discipline;
- has demonstrated a critical self-reflective attitude, an active commitment, a large autonomy and to be able to work in a team (if applicable).

1.3 Supervision and mentoring

During their Master's thesis, students are provided with qualitative guidance. All Master's students have a Master's thesis advisor, usually a professor associated with their Master's programme. Besides, students are guided by a teaching assistant, who is more closely connected to the Master's thesis and acts as a mentor for the student.

There is regular contact between the student and his mentor, usually (but not always) on a weekly or biweekly basis. The mentor tracks the progress of the student and acts as a first access point for advice and other resources. However, all initiatives on reports and progress meetings must come from the student. Besides regular meetings with the mentor, students meet their advisor at least once or twice per semester. Thus, the mentor has a close understanding of the Master's thesis progress and informs the advisor regularly.

In some cases the coaching can also be performed by the advisor himself. When the Master's thesis is done in close collaboration with a company or other organisation, the student will be coached both by an employee of the company, as well as by a faculty member of Engineering Science. During the academic year, the students are asked to formally report on the progress of the Master's thesis. Depending on the programme this can be done once or twice during the year. Furthermore, depending on the programme, the students are asked to keep track of the work they have done, e.g. through a time sheet or a blog.

As the teaching assistants play an important role in the guidance of the Master's thesis student, the Faculty provides qualitative educational training sessions, described in detail in paragraph 2. Furthermore a memorandum describing the Faculty's vision of qualitative mentoring was written. Specific attention was given to the different roles and responsibilities of mentors as well as promoters.

1.4 Reporting skills

The main deliverable of the Master's thesis is the Master's thesis text, which can include appendices with descriptions of code or experimental data. In some programmes, also a paper is required, or a paper/poster in a style appropriate for a non-specialist audience. The Master's thesis can be submitted at three moments of the academic year: June 6th, August 21st, and January 15th. In some programmes intermediate deliverables, such as a literature review, are required.

To enhance the quality of these reports, The Educational Development Unit of the Faculty, in co-operation with the University Library, organises Master's Thesis workshops about information literacy, intellectual integrity and plagiarism and academic writing. These workshops aim to support the writing process of the Master's thesis:

- Workshop to recapitulate on literature search in the library and its extensive e-collections (Information Literacy);
- Workshop to refresh the principles on academic writing (Academic Writing);
- Workshop on integrity

1.5 Evaluation

The evaluation of the Master's thesis applies both to the process and the product and is done by a commission that consists of the advisor, the mentor and two additional assessors with sufficient expertise.

Each student has to give a final presentation of at least 15 minutes, and answer to the questions of the jury during an oral defence.

To ensure the quality and consistency of the evaluation of the Master's theses, the Faculty developed an evaluation sheet (table 1) and an assessment Scale (table 2). Table 2 is not a grading matrix, but contains criteria that have to help the assessors situate the master's thesis within the different aspects. The final obtained mark is a

weighted average of these different aspects. The evaluation sheet of table 1 needs to help jury members weigh the various aspects of the thesis in order to reach a final score.

Table 2. Evaluation sheet

	Insufficient	Poor	OK	Good	Very good	Excellent
Global evaluation						
1 Research aspect						
1.1 Content i.e. <i>Research question</i> <i>Review of literature</i> <i>Approach and methodology</i> <i>Interpretation of the results obtained</i> <i>Conclusions</i>						
1.2 Final report i.e. <i>Accuracy</i> <i>Intelligibility</i> <i>Depth</i> <i>Style</i> <i>Language</i> <i>Lay-out</i> <i>Tables and figures</i> <i>References</i>						
1.3 Presentation i.e. <i>State of the art</i> <i>Presentation</i> <i>Explanation</i> <i>Language</i> <i>Time management</i> And the defence i.e. <i>Answers to the questions</i> <i>Defensibility</i> <i>Clarification</i>						
2 Additional assignment						
3 Method i.e. <i>Dedication</i> <i>Planning</i> <i>Autonomy</i> <i>Half-term report</i> <i>Teamwork</i>						

Table 1: Assessment scale

Score	Research quality, personal contribution and originality	Insight into the subject matter	Methodology	Quality of text and presentation	Histogr.*
19-20	Master's thesis of high research quality that exceeds expectations.	The student has insight and can discuss with experts within the domain.	A correct methodology was used, characteristic of the discipline.	Text and presentation of excellent quality.	0.9%
18-18.9	The personal contribution is high and the work is characterized by a high level of originality from the student.				3.9%
17-17.9	Master's thesis of good research quality. The personal contribution is high and/or the work is characterized by a high level of originality from the student.	The student has insight and can carry on a meaningful discussion with the members of the jury.	A correct methodology was used, characteristic of the discipline.	Text and presentation of very good quality.	11.1%
16-16.9	The quality of the master's thesis meets the expectations. The personal contribution and/or the work is characterized by a good degree of originality from the student.				12.3%
15-15.9	The quality of the master's thesis meets the expectations. The personal contribution and/or the work is characterized by a good degree of originality from the student.	The student has insight and can have a discussion, albeit limited.	A correct methodology was used, characteristic of the discipline.	Text and presentation of good quality.	19.2%
14-14.9	The quality of the master's thesis meets the expectations. The degree of personal contribution is limited and the work is characterized by a rather limited degree of originality from the student.				17.2%
13-13.9	The quality of the master's thesis meets the expectations. The degree of personal contribution is limited and the work is characterized by a rather limited degree of originality from the student.	The student has mastered the topic, but has no insight into the wider domain.	A correct methodology was used, characteristic of the discipline.	Text and/or presentation of moderate quality.	12.9%
12-12.9	The quality of the master's thesis only just meets the expectations. No personal contribution has been made and the work is characterized by a very low degree of originality from the student.				8.4%
11-11.9	Poor, but remediable in the short term. The amount of work and/or the reasoning does not meet the expectations.	The student has only mastered the subject to a limited extent.	Small methodological mistakes that do not influence the conclusions of the work.	Text and/or presentation are poor.	6.6%
10-10.9	The student has not mastered the subject.				5.1%
9-9.9	Poor, but remediable in the short term. The amount of work and/or the reasoning does not meet the expectations.	The student has not mastered the subject.	The conclusions of the work are questionable.	Text and/or presentation of insufficient quality.	0.9%
8-8.9	The student has not mastered the subject.				0.5%
<8	Poor, not remediable in the short term. The amount of work and/or the reasoning does not meet the expectations.	The student has not mastered the subject.	The conclusions of the work are questionable.	Text and/or presentation of insufficient quality.	0.9% *2012-'15

2 EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT PROGRAMME FOR SUPERVISING TEACHING ASSISTANTS

2.1 Training?

Every academic year, about 200 new PhD students start their research at The Faculty of Engineering Science. Most of them will teach students and coach Master's theses. Therefore, the Faculty provides an educational training programme for these teaching assistants (TAs). In September 2014, the new training programme SWEET² or 'Starters Week of Engineering and Education: Training for TAs' was introduced. Besides enhancing the TAs' teaching skills, the improvement of the quality of education is aspired. The guiding principle in developing this TA training is the 'teach as you preach' principle.

SWEET² consists of a number of thematic training modules organised during the first week of each semester. Every training module consists of two 2-hour sessions and two corresponding preparatory assignments. These sessions focus on dealing with frequently occurring problems, activating students, providing feedback, and the implementation of modern technology in the teaching practice. The first session strives for providing TAs advice before they start their teaching assignment. During the second session, the emphasis is reflection on their teaching experience and feedback. In order to enable more interaction between the TAs and to facilitate peer learning during the TA training, we introduced blended learning by asking the TAs to make a preparatory assignment before each session.

According to the 'teach as you preach' principle, each module departs from one specific teaching format that corresponds to the teaching practice of the TAs, such as supervising exercise sessions or coaching Problem-based Learning. During the sessions the SWEET²-coaches utilise teaching methods that are considered desirable to be put into practice by the TAs during their own teaching assignment.

2.2 Specific training module 'Guiding a Master's thesis'

Within the training module Guiding a Master's thesis, the importance of clear agreements is highlighted and the TAs receive tips and tricks on guiding a student. In accordance with the 'teach as you preach' principle, the teaching formats refer to the one-to-one relationship of the TA with the student. During a roleplay for example, cases are given and the participants should react as a TA or a student. Besides, the structure of the module corresponds to the different steps in the Master's thesis process throughout the academic year, like defining the subject, getting started and giving feedback.

2.3 Evaluation of the module 'Guiding a Master's thesis'

The module 'Guiding a Master's thesis' was implemented in its current format in September 2015. To ensure the quality of the sessions and to further optimize them, the instructors asked the participants to write down three positive aspects and three points that need improvement, after each session organised during the SWEET²-weeks of September 2015, February 2016 and September 2016.

Overall, the feedback of the participants was positive, as shown in tables 3. 74% of the participants gave 3 positive remarks, whereas almost 51% gave less than 2 negative remarks. The interactive format was thoroughly appreciated (62%) out of 193 participants. The 'teach as you preach' principle, was recognised and mentioned explicitly as positive by 5% of the respondents. The materials used during the sessions turned out to be helpful, as 34% of the respondents mentioned them. In particular a testimonial video where professors explain their view on guiding Master's theses was inspiring for 19% of the respondents. 6% of the respondents would even like to see more of these videos. The concept of student archetypes,

developed to help identify different types of students and how to adapt your communication style accordingly was appreciated by 20% of the respondents. Another positive aspect was the use of hands-on guidelines and tips (18%). However 18% of the respondents would wish to discuss more examples of real-life cases.

In September 2015 13% of the respondents acknowledged that the relevance of some of the exercises was not always clear to them. In order to improve this, efforts were made to make the relevance of the exercises and the cohesion of the session more clear to the participants. This resulted in a more positive evaluation of that aspect in February and September 2016, respectively 23% and 22% of the participants mentioned the cohesion and relevance of the exercises as a positive aspect.

Table 3: Number of remarks 'Guiding a Master's thesis'

	3 remarks	2 remarks	1 remark	0 remarks
Sessions (# 193)				
Positive	74,09%	23,32%	2,59%	0,00%
Negative	23,83%	25,39%	41,97%	8,81%

3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

All efforts in terms of refining admission procedures, formulating learning outcomes, developing a learning pathway regarding reporting skills, evaluation and mentoring students resulted in a supported and coherent framework. This framework allows the faculty to continuously monitor and develop the quality of the master's theses without compromising each programme own habits and traditions.

Maintaining and continuing this framework is one of the challenges for the Faculty in the future. In this perspective, the FCMT is the key actor in coordinating all the different aspects and stakeholders involved. It is important to allow the committee to establish an efficient quality developing process while keeping a balance between bottom-up and top-down concerns. In the future, a relapse to the original more administrative and practical mandate can be considered as a thread and should be avoided. Therefore, close attention will be paid to keep the FMCT's mandate content-focused.

In this paper specific attention was given to the development and evaluation of the educational support programme for TAs mentoring theses. The implementation was successful and the participants evaluated the training module positively. As discussed above, the possibility to interact during the sessions was highly appreciated by the TAs: working in group, sharing experiences and discussing problems that occur during their teaching assignment were mentioned as positive aspects. Furthermore, the respondents gave positive comments about the content, teaching formats and materials used during the sessions.

Efforts were made to make the rationale and cohesion of the session explicit, which was successfully proven by the subsequent evaluations. In the nearby future, more elaborated use of real-life cases is a suggestion that will be taken into account by SWEET²-coaches to further improve the module.

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